

Comparative analysis of machine learning algorithms for the classification of underwater marine debris

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Abstract—Marine debris is considered as a global problem and a major threat to the ecosystem and its inhabitants. To address this issue, it is important to identify these densely polluted areas inside the sea and most importantly at the seabed. In this study, we compare the traditional machine learning techniques for the classification of marine debris located deep in the sea and at the sea bed, with the aim of performing monitoring task in an automated manner. Convolutional neural network based architectures are employed for the features detection, followed by Random forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Logistic Regression (LR), eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGB) and Neural Networks (NN) based classification. The comparative analysis is performed and the primary evaluation index, accuracy indicates that NN, SVM and LR using DenseNet architecture as a fixed feature extractor achieved higher test accuracy of 84%, 82% and 81% respectively. XGB classifier showed the best performance with ResNet50 network with an accuracy of 75%. Based on our findings NN and SVM are considered as the best predictors for the present deep sea marine litter dataset using DenseNet as a feature extractor.

Index Terms—Marine debris, Underwater Pollution, Convolutional Neural Networks, Random Forest, Neural Networks, Logistic Regression, Extreme Gradient Boosting

I. INTRODUCTION

Marine debris is defined as a material that enter into the sea through multiple sources and are harmful for marine environment. It is considered as a widespread problem and a major threat to the health of the oceans and its inhabitants. This waste entering the sea includes food packaging, plastic bottles, metallic can *etc.* The pathway begins when these litter objects enter into the sea/ocean directly or indirectly and ultimately settle at the seabed. According to the European environment agency, land-based sources count for 80% of the marine litter and approximately 85% of that is plastic [1]. There is an urgent need to develop innovative solutions to fight against the negative impact of this waste, which is extremely harmful not only for the sea life but also for the human health. It is of extreme importance to monitor these densely polluted areas, compare data from continually observed systems and perform actions based on the outcome. Traditionally, the monitoring of debris is performed by human observers, which is a time consuming process and an enormous human effort is required. With the recent advancement in the field of Artificial Intelligence (AI), the machine learning based algorithms are

widely used in different fields including medical imaging, remote sensing, agricultural and industrial applications *etc.*, due to their precise performance and high accuracy. In this regard, to expedite the monitoring task, the efficient and effective solution would be to track these polluted areas through the AI based systems. Several AI based methods are proposed in the past to classify litter objects from the surface of the oceans, beaches and shores. Marin *et al.* developed the model for autonomous marine debris identification and classification. State-of-the-art deep convolutional architectures are compared for marine debris classification [2]. Paula *et al.* presented a bibliographic survey of techniques and sensors used to detect marine litter and conclude that most studies have used satellite platforms to target plastics through remote sensing techniques [3]. Recently, Hidaka *et al.* used semantic segmentation to detect marine litter, the authors indicate that the patterns with a small number of features in the training data may reduce the segmentation performance [4]. During the last few years, Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) and drones are mostly employed for the monitoring and data collection tasks. Martin *et al.* presented a method for marine litter recognition on beaches using images acquired through UAV. The method examined RF classifier to detect beach litter from orthomosaics [5]. Similarly, Papakonstantinou *et al.* combined drone technology with machine learning to create marine litter density maps to monitor litter objects on the beach and nearshore [6]. Gonçalves *et al.* explored machine learning methods to automate marine litter detection on the data acquired from UAV. They used RF classifier along with the pixel-by-pixel classification technique to explore marine litter objects [7]. Fulton *et al.* presented the comparison of deep-learning algorithms in performing the task of visually detecting trash in realistic underwater environments by evaluating the training performance of YOLOv2 network [8]. Similarly, Musi *et al.* presented a study on the performance of different neural network architectures for underwater litter detection in the marine environment [9]. They generated the dataset from web based images. Synthetic underwater images were constructed by putting artificial litter objects into real underwater background image and evaluated the training performance using YOLO networks. There exist several other methods to detect marine debris from the sea surface, beaches

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of marine debris classification pipeline.

and its shores, but based on the bibliographic survey, to the best of our knowledge, the application of machine learning algorithms on the detection and classification of underwater marine litter is in its early stage. Although, several methods exist for the detection of litter objects on the sea surfaces and mostly the data is acquired through the camera mounted on the drones/UAVs. However, this study aims to investigate machine learning algorithms for the classification of underwater marine debris in real environment that yield more accurate results. We used transfer learning based network architectures *e.g.*, ResNet50, VGG19 and DenseNet to extract features from underwater images (deep sea or at sea-bed) containing litter objects, followed by the classification using traditional machine learning classifiers. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: The methodology of the processing is given in section II. We present the theoretical background of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) architecture based feature extraction in section III. In section IV, the detailed explanation of machine learning based classifiers is presented. Section V presents the comparative analysis and performance of the classifiers. Section VI finally concludes the paper with future extension.

II. METHODOLOGY

The methodology studied in this paper is based on pre-trained CNNs as a feature extractor and supervised learning based classifiers to distinguish litter objects in the dataset. The schematic illustration of the processing is given in Fig. 1. In the first step, data splitting and pre-processing is applied. The network identifies the points of interest from the given training set, termed as features extraction. The classification step group the features extracted via CNN based architectures to distinct groups of unique characteristics termed as classes. The algorithms discussed in this paper include Random forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Logistic Regression (LR), eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGB) and Neural Networks (NN). In the coming sections, we present the details of processing steps of each algorithm.

A. Data Set and Pre-processing

The dataset used in this work is derived from the database of “The Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology (JAMSTEC)” [10]. They provided deep sea debris database,

which contains marine debris videos and images, available for litter object detection. The dataset contains total of 1,918 images belonging to *six* classes: *Glass, Metal, Plastic, Rubber, Other* and *No trash*, the litter objects were identified manually and labeled for each class. Fig. 2 illustrate the frequency of the data along with the images containing litter objects of each class. For the feature extraction, data normalization is performed as it directly influences the performance of the predictive model where the data values of the features differs significantly. Although some techniques *e.g.*, RF are more robust but to perform the comparative analysis, data pre-processing is applied prior to the training step. Pre-processing includes normalization of data dimension, colour, contrast/smoothness (local variations) *etc.*

Fig. 2. Frequency and examples of raw images of each class sourced from JAMSTEC-library of Deep-Sea images.

III. CNN BASED FEATURE EXTRACTION

Feature selection is the process of finding optimal data points which represent given set of data. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) based feature learning is commonly used in several applications. These networks take advantage of the spatial information of the images *e.g.*, their structure and local properties. Currently, CNNs are the most extensively studied network architecture, which take image as an input, followed by multiple filtering to differentiate objects from each other with better accuracy as compared to the other classification algorithms. Gu *et al.* provided an extensive survey of the recent advances in the field of CNNs [11]. The convolutional layers learn feature representations of the inputs and composed of several convolution kernels to compute different feature

maps [11]. Specifically, each neuron of a feature map is connected to a region of neighbouring neurons in the previous layer. The new feature map can be obtained by first convolving the input with a learned kernel and then applying an element-wise nonlinear activation function on the convolved results and to generate each feature map, the kernel is shared by all spatial locations of the input. The complete feature maps are obtained by using several different kernels. Mathematically, the feature value at location (i, j) in the k -th feature map of l -th layer, $z_{i,j,k}^l$, is calculated by [11]:

$$z_{i,j,k}^l = w_k^{lT} x_{i,j}^l + b_k^l \quad (1)$$

where w_k^l and b_k^l are the weight vector and bias term of the k -th filter of the l -th layer respectively, and $x_{i,j}^l$ is the input patch centered at location (i, j) of the l -th layer. The activation value $a_{i,j,k}^l$ of convolutional feature $z_{i,j,k}^l$ can be computed as [11]:

$$a_{i,j,k}^l = a(z_{i,j,k}^l) \quad (2)$$

The pooling layers aggregate information within feature map by replacing local pooling regions with the maximum element in the case of max pooling. We applied transfer learning-based approach, where the model is pre-trained on the features of 1.2 million training images from 1000 classes of ImageNet data. We applied three pre-trained network architectures for the feature selection purposes as a fixed feature extractor, where the weights of the networks are frozen for the current application. The obtained feature vector sizes are 512, 1024 and 2048 of VGG19, DenseNet121 and ResNet50 respectively.

IV. CLASSIFICATION ALGORITHMS

We applied machine learning classifiers by using the set of extracted features to fit the data and to generate outcomes. The supervised learning algorithms studied in this work are widely used in other classification tasks and due to their precise performance, in this study we evaluate their performance on the classification of marine debris in under water environment. The brief overview of these classifiers is discussed in the following section.

A. Support Vector Machine (SVM)

SVM is a supervised machine learning algorithm that can be used for both linear and non-linear separable features. Traditionally, the algorithm selects the surface that lies equidistant from the nearest vector spaces and classify the dataset in classes by calculating the margin between each class with support vectors [12]. For several classes, the most common algorithm is based on ‘‘one versus all’’ approach where a classifier is trained for each class. In this work, *RBF kernel*, commonly used in SVM classification problems is used [12].

B. EXtreme Gradient Boost (XGB)

XGBoost is ensemble supervised learning algorithm, based on the gradient boosting decision tree. The algorithm is built on the principle of the gradient boosting framework

for the classification and regression purposes by combining weak learners into a stronger learner using iteration. XGBoost and random forest are integration algorithms based on the decision tree. Boosting algorithm builds weak learners one by one, accumulating multiple weak learners through continuous iteration [12] [16].

C. Random Forest (RF)

Random forest is a supervised, ensemble machine learning algorithm that integrates multiple trees through the bagging idea [13], [14]. The predictions of all those decision trees are then taken into consideration for a voting criterion and the predicted output of the classifier is the class with maximum votes. In this study, hyper parameters e.g. estimators, depth are determined by using grid search methods. The classifier uses Ginni Index for attribute selection, it gauges the impurity of an attribute with respect to classes [14]. For a given dataset T , selecting one item of the dataset (pixel) at random and telling that the item is belonging to class C_i , the Ginni Index can be written as:

$$Obj = \sum_{j=1} \sum \left(\frac{f(C_i, T)}{|T|} \right) \left(\frac{f(C_j, T)}{|T|} \right) \quad (3)$$

where $\frac{f(C_i, T)}{|T|}$ is the probability that the selected case belongs to class C_i

D. Logistic Regression (LR)

Logistic Regression is considered as an effective and widely used method for binary classification problems. LR establishes a regression formula and a sigmoid function nested based on this multiple linear regression model [12]. In LR, given N instances x_i , where $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, the m features of the input instance $\mathbf{x}_i = (x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{im})$, are combined linearly using coefficients β_0 and $\beta_i = (\beta_{i1}, \beta_{i2}, \dots, \beta_{im})$ to predict the classification outcome y_i . Specifically, given an input instance \mathbf{x}_i , the probability that $y_i = 1$ is denoted by $p(\mathbf{x}_i)$ and is modelled with the standard logistic regression model as follows [12]:

$$p(\mathbf{x}_i) = \left\{ \frac{e^{(\beta_0 + \beta * \mathbf{x}_i)}}{1 + e^{(\beta_0 + \beta * \mathbf{x}_i)}} \right\} \quad (4)$$

The aim of LR is to find the best parameters β_0 and β to determine the best fitting model that describes the relationship between the input features and the predicted class value [12].

E. Neural Network Model (NN)

Neural Network is an effective supervised machine learning technique for the problems that can be defined either linearly or non-linearly [15]. The algorithm learns from the data provided for training purposes through feed forward and back propagation process. The network is mainly composed of input, layers and hidden units, and is generally trained in an iterative mode by modifying connection weights, nonlinear activation functions e.g. *Relu* and deviations until the loss between the output generated by the network and the expected is within the specified range. The number of hidden units defined the complexity of the model.

Fig. 3. Statistics of the Accuracy index (%) of each algorithm.

V. SIMULATIONS AND DISCUSSION

We investigated well-known network architectures including ResNet50, DenseNet121 and VGG19 with traditional machine learning classifiers for the classification of underwater litter objects. Networks were trained using Keras on top of Tensor Flow 2.2 environment. The pre-trained weights of all three architectures directly obtained from Keras library were trained as a fixed feature extractor scheme on marine debris dataset. On top of the fixed feature extraction layers, machine learning classifiers learn underlying patterns through features extracted from training set and discriminate data accordingly. To evaluate the performance of the classification algorithms, accuracy, precision and F1 score are considered as an evaluation parameters. *Accuracy* refers to the proportion of all correctly predicted outcome (including positive samples and negative samples) in the total data and *Precision* represents the the correct positive prediction [17].

Recall is the number of correct positive results divided by the number of positive results that should have been returned. *F1-score* is obtained by the weighted harmonic average of precision and recall due to the contradiction between the two evaluation indexes and is formulated as [17]:

$$F1 = \left\{ \frac{2PR}{P + R} \right\} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 4. Class-wise precision of classifiers with three feature extraction scheme on test data.

Fig. 3 summarizes the evaluation of three models on the test data with multiple classification techniques. Among the traditional machine learning classifiers, SVM achieved highest accuracy 82% by using DenseNet as a feature extraction model, followed by the LR with the accuracy of

Fig. 5. Class-wise F1-score of classifiers with three feature extraction scheme on test data

81%. Similarly, feature extracted with ResNet architecture achieved comparable accuracy of 78% and 77% by using SVM and LR classifiers while RF and XGB lag behind with the accuracy of 70% and 74% respectively. Feature extracted from VGG19 architecture obtained the maximum accuracy of 72% with SVM classification model. The performance of all the network architecture improves with NN classifier and achieved 84% accuracy with the DenseNet based feature extraction. In certain areas, the existence of one particular type of litter objects can be more than the other. In such situation, the effective solution would be to utilize the classification method which performed best for that particular category. To examine the class-wise performance, Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 illustrate the precision and F1-score of litter classes using different types of classification models. In general, litter objects in the test data are correctly classified with *Rubber* and *Glass* objects achieved highest precision and F1 score due to their distinctive shape features, followed by the *Metal* and *Plastic* objects. There is a significant in-class variance in plastic and metal categories due to the fact that the shape of the plastic and metal (cylindrical and rectangular and similarly for plastic includes plastic bags and disposable glasses *etc.*) but still the studied model achieved higher accuracy with the limited dataset. Fig. 6 presents an overview of the methods given in literature for different types of trash and litter objects for domestic and industrial applications. In comparison to these methods, the obtained accuracy for underwater litter objects is comparable with all these classifiers considering the fact that the underwater images has low contrast and insufficient illumination. Fig. 7 shows the normalized confusion matrices of four classification scheme, where in most of the cases, the model achieved the prediction score of no less than 75% and correctly classified the litter objects except in the case of other trash category which is a more general class.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a comparative analysis to predict marine debris with data pre-processing (to eliminate dimension and variation effects), feature extraction and supervised learning-based classification. The prediction results using multiple classifiers were compared using CNNs based pre-trained architecture as a feature extractors. It is observed that DenseNet121, Resnet50 and VGG19 achieved higher evaluation index with NN models, followed by the SVM and LR. The obtained metrics indicate that NN based framework are the most

Author	Trash type	Classifier	Acc (%)
Gómez <i>et al.</i>	Solid domestic waste	LR	78
		KNN	77
		SVM	81
Mandar <i>et al.</i>	Trash items (Paper, Plastic, Metal, Glass)	KNN	52
		RF	63
		XGB	70
		SVM	66
Hanbal <i>et al.</i>	Biodegradable trash	RF	97
		SVM	89
		NN	86
Sami <i>et al.</i>	Trash items (Paper, Plastic, Metal, Glass)	SVM	85
		RF	55
		DT	65
		NN	90

Fig. 6. Comparison of the performance with few methods given in the literature [18], [19], [20], [21].

Fig. 7. Normalized confusion matrices of SVM, XGB, LR and NN with DenseNet and ResNet50 architectures.

suitable for the detection of underwater marine pollution with relatively larger dataset. Among traditional machine learning algorithms, the most noticeable is SVM and LR with the accuracy of 82% and 81% respectively. Therefore, for the given dataset with significant in-class variance, NN and SVM are considered as the best predictors for the marine litter classification. Overall the obtained results indicate that current techniques performed well for the monitoring of underwater marine debris. In future, the focus will be on the development of end-to-end model to perform monitoring task in real time at the edge devices.

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